

Flatworm Regeneration And Reactionary Behavior Towards Food Source During Different Timespans

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Abstract. Flatworms are known for their ability to regenerate due to their pluripotent stem cells. Newer organs and systematic life functions can be produced from the remnants of the flatworm and eventually form an entirely new flatworm. However, previous studies have indicated that regeneration was impossible without brain tissue. This implies that in flatworm regeneration, only the head part of the flatworm that contains a brain-like structure and nervous tissue could regenerate, and the body portion without the brain tissues would eventually dissolve or die. However, in my experiment, it is discovered that the body could also regenerate regardless of whether there is brain tissue present in the part of the body severed. Additionally, the studies also indicated that the regenerated portion would lack the necessary life functions. However, after 6 days of regeneration, the sliced flatworm, or at least its head, was able to target the food source and reach it quite well. Therefore, my results do not support the theory that flatworms without brain tissue were not able to produce organs with vital life functions.

1. Introduction

Flatworms, in this case *Paucumara* sp., are soft-bodied flattened invertebrates that are bilaterally symmetric. They have no specific body cavity or specialized organ system, but instead, their bodies are made out of a substance called parenchyma, a spongy connective tissue, that fills in the space between the organs in the flatworm. Despite being seen as more primitive, flatworms do have a head region with concentrated nervous tissue acting as their brain. Most of them are hermaphroditic, though sexual reproduction is also possible. Ecologically, flatworms can be found anywhere with moisture, but generally within marine environments. The genus *Paucumara* specifically lives in salt water and are free-living organisms ranging from about 1.5×0.5 mm up to 2.75×1 mm^[1]. In previous studies, scientists have found that flatworms can rebuild parts of the body after amputation, or removal of their body part, using pluripotent stem cells, which are specialized cells that are able to develop into more than 200 hundred types of functional cell bodies. Pluripotent stem cells can form tissues resembling many functions rather than simply developing into one type of cell. The cells can regenerate after amputation because their “neoblasts are reactivated” and can “migrate to the wound”, forming “blastema”^[2] that eventually turns into more complex structures that are previously a part of the flatworm. Previous studies have demonstrated that they have a time span of 65 days^[3] to regenerate completely. However, previous studies neglected the time it takes for the digestive organs to regrow and allow proper digestive function of the flatworm. This experiment is set up to determine the time span at which the flatworm responds to food sources as a result of their digestive regeneration and the complete duration as well.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sampling Site and Methods

Four saltwater flatworms (*Paucumara*) were extracted from the saltwater container in the lab culture and each flatworm was moved onto a 7 cm diameter petri dish with a pipette by sucking one flatworm up at a time and transferring them to a petri dish. Each flatworm was transferred to a separate petri dish, with a total of 4 petri dishes with complete flatworms and 2 extra petri dishes that were left on the side for the preparation of further procedural steps. The petri dishes served as observational containers to record the behaviors of the flatworm and should be evenly distributed with water to ensure the free movement of the flatworm across the petri dish.

2.2. Laboratory Setup

Using a permanent marker, one petri dish with a flatworm was labeled as “Un sliced, food” and another petri dish with a flatworm as “Un sliced, no food” and was set aside. This was for the purpose of differentiating the samples. The petri dishes labeled “unsliced” would contain the flatworms that were not cut, while the ones labeled “food” would represent the petri dishes containing flatworms that would be fed with pig liver. These flatworms would act as controls for regeneration. Next, one of the unlabeled petri dishes would be opened and a scalpel should be prepared. To slice the flatworm in half, the scalpel was carefully held, and the flatworm was placed in the middle of the petri dish to help determine the approximate half of the flatworm. Then, the flatworm was sliced in half horizontally using the scalpel, and the body part of the sliced half was transferred into one of the two extra petri dishes prepared. The petri dish was filled with evenly spread water to make sure proper movement of the flatworm. The petri dish where the flatworm was sliced was labeled “head, no food” because it contained the head of the flatworm, while the petri dish where the body part was placed should be labeled “body, no food”. These would serve as the experimental groups of the regeneration part of the experiment while being the control group for the reaction towards food part of the experiment. These petri dishes should be set aside, and the last remaining petri dish was taken out. The flatworm contained within this petri dish was sliced in the same way as the previous sliced flatworm, and the body part of this flatworm was again sucked up by a pipette and transferred to another empty petri dish labeled with “Body, food,” meaning that the flatworm in this petri dish would be fed with liver and observed. The previous petri dish where this flatworm was sliced was labeled “Head, food” because it contained the head of the flatworm and was to be fed with liver. These two dishes serve as the experimental group for both regeneration and reaction to food.

2.3. Experimentation

On the first day of observation, the petri dishes labeled with “food”, or the experimental groups for the reaction to food part of the experiment, were observed for their reaction to food. The petri dish was put in a place without much light variations, and a piece of raw pig liver of about 2 cm long was placed in the center of the petri dish that reads “unsliced, food”. Then, the cap of the petri dish with the pig liver was put onto the surface with the white bottom to ensure a clear view of the flatworm’s path. A recording device was placed on a stable and unmoving object, a box in this case, with the camera exposed that takes the entire petri dish into view. The recording started and continued until the flatworm reaches the liver. The steps labeling the Petri dishes were repeated but written as “Head, food” and “body, food”. For these experimental groups, the time for recording their movements is maximally 15 min. Once the time got to 15 min, the recording was stopped.

For the next 5 days, the amount of regeneration happening to the sliced flatworms are recorded by taking a picture of them with a measuring instrument (e.g. ruler, finger, etc.) to determine the amount of growth.

After 6 days, do another experiment as was done on the first day of the flatworm's reaction to pig liver with what remained of the flatworm in the petri dishes labeled "unsliced, food", "head, food" and "body, food." Record the results again with the same device and same equipment to ensure the lack of confounding variables. Observe changes and abnormalities compared to the previous results that were taken on the first day of the experiment.

3. Results

3.1. Records of the flatworms on the first day they were cut

Figure 1 showed the control group of the reaction to food part of the experiment. Observations of its behavior towards food would be recorded to be compared with the sliced halves of this experiment. Figure 2 represented the control group for the regeneration part of the experiment. It would neither be sliced nor given food. Figure 3 showed the already sliced flatworm's head. This served as the experimental group for regeneration and reaction to food. This meant that its regenerating behavior and reaction to food would all be recorded and observed. Figure 4 was cut from the same flatworm as Figure 3, and this body part of the flatworm was a control group for the food reaction part but an experimental group for the regeneration part. This meant that it would not be given food but would be observed under the microscope its process of regeneration.

Figure 1. Unsliced flatworm under microscope with magnification of 4x. Petri dish labeled "Unsliced, food"

Figure 2. Unsliced flatworm under microscope with magnification of 4x. Petri dish labeled "Unsliced, no food"

Figure 3. Sliced flatworm's head under microscope with magnification of 4x. Petri dish labeled "Head, food".

Figure 4. Sliced flatworm's body under microscope with magnification of 4x. Petri dish labeled "Body, no food".

3.2. Control Group Experimentation

The control group of the experiment demonstrated the proper time that the flatworm was supposed to reach the target food source. The flatworm in Figure 5 took around 1 minute to complete its route to the food source. This supposedly indicates that it would take the regenerated flatworms around the same time or longer to reach the food source. Unfortunately, because the flatworm in the petri dish labeled "body, no food" has disappeared, likely dissolved, only the experimentation for the sliced flatworm head as shown in Figure 6 could be done. As demonstrated, the flatworm head had no reaction towards the pig liver in 8 minutes, as it remained stationery for the whole time. This either meant that either their digestive organ prevented any reactions to the food source, or their time of regeneration was too short for them to respond properly because of a lack of digestive system.

Figure 5. Unsliced flatworm's path within 1'14" minute towards the food source.

Petri dish Labeled "Unsliced, food". The red dots each represent a short stopping place of the flatworm, and connected together it represents the entire path of the flatworm towards the food source.

Figure 6. Sliced flatworm's head's reaction

to pig liver in 8 minutes. Petri Dish labeled "Head, food".

3.3. Third Day - Observations Of Regenerating Flatworms

The third day marked that the experiment was halfway through. In Figure 7 the flatworm has an already complete and healthy inner organ system as was observed. The outline of the flatworm can be seen as clear and smooth, though a specialized head system and nervous system wasn't observed to have existed and successfully regenerated yet. This flatworm would be tested towards food on the sixth day, the final day of the experiment. Figure 8 was similar to the circumstances in Figure 7. It could be observed that there were evident signs of regeneration on the left corner of the picture, behind the head of the flatworm. However, the regenerated structure looked transparent without internal organs, therefore, it was assumed that the regeneration was possibly incomplete. The full development of organ systems of the flatworm would mark the completion of regeneration.

Figure 7. Sliced flatworm's body
under microscope with magnification of 4x. Petri
Dish labeled "Body, food".

Figure 8. Sliced flatworm's head
under microscope with magnification of 4x. Petri Dish
labeled "Head, no food".

However, the experiment encountered an obstacle. Again, one of the flatworm specimens dissolved as shown in Figure 9. This was the flatworm that was shown in Figure 6. The fact that it dissolved possibly means that its vital organs for maintaining its body cavity, were cut off from the head, preventing it from having a reaction towards the food source. The cause of its dissolution was narrowed down to two: contamination of the petri dish, or improper management of microscope equipment. Regardless of the mistake, an assumption was made: the flatworm couldn't have already developed the vital organs before dissolution, or else it would *have at least moved during the food reaction test. Its immobility suggested its ending.*

Figure 9. Remnants of a sliced flatworm's head
under microscope with magnification of 4x. Petri Dish labeled "Head, food".
The two dots most likely resembled the eyes of the flatworm.

3.4. Sixth Day - Results Of Regeneration

On the sixth day, the sliced flatworms finally regenerated and formed a complete body cavity as demonstrated in figure 10. This flatworm successfully developed internal organs and was seemingly continuing to grow its tails and the rest of its body pretty well. Therefore, it could be concluded that a week is about the time at which flatworms could successfully regenerate. Figure 11 showed the flatworm that acted as control for the food reaction experiment.

Figure 10. Sliced flatworm head regenerated observed under microscope with magnification of 4x. Petri Dish labeled “Head, no food”.

Figure 11. Unsliced flatworm. Petri dish labeled “Unsliced, food”.

A. curled up flatworm. B. stretched out flatworm.

Experimentation of the flatworm’s reaction to food source was shown in Figure 12. Because of the lost of two experimental groups, this was the only result gotten for the food reaction

experiment. It can be seen from the image and its description that the body part of the sliced flatworm remained immobile when the unsliced flatworm has already reached the target. Judging from the size of the body part of the flatworm and the reaction speed and movement, the body regenerated much slower than the head part, and the body did not display any forms of reaction to food. This most likely represents that the eyes and the mouth portion of its digestive system haven't developed yet, therefore it would not react to the food source properly as did the unsliced flatworm.

Figure 12. Unsliced flatworm reaction to food vs. sliced flatworm body reaction to food.

Petri dish label shown in the image. Blue circle represents the unsliced flatworm next to the food source after 1 minute. Red circle represents the sliced flatworm body unmoving after 1 minute.

4. Discussion

Ultimately, for the regeneration experiment, we know that it would take approximately a week for the head to regenerate, but because of time limits, the body took much longer than the head, and accurate data was unable to be collected. However, it was estimated that the body would take about 2 times longer than the head because it lacked a nervous system. However, though, the pluripotent stem cells as mentioned in the introduction section served to be well specializations of the process of regeneration.

Additionally, for the food reaction experiment, it could be seen that the regenerated flatworms still could not respond to the food source, while the control group behaves in the stable way of heading towards the food in about 1 minute. Therefore, it can be concluded

that 7 days was not enough for the sliced flatworm to develop necessary organs. For the head it would be the digestive system. For the body it would be the nervous system that directs movement and the head that contains the mouth.

Past studies have indicated that vital organs are required in order for flatworms to retrieve their life functions after regeneration. According to Tamara Schadt ^[4] “as long as the brain remained at least partially intact,” flatworms would be able to regenerate and develop vital organs such as the mouth, intestines, etc. However, data from the experiment has shown that despite the lack of brain tissue, the body of the flatworm could regenerate but in the expanse of regeneration speed and efficiency. Flatworms regenerated from the body part took longer to regain mobility. Not only were the body able to regenerate, but the head was able to move within a time frame of 6 days. This was against Schadt’s claim that “amputated parts of the brain could not be regenerated.”

The organisms’ response to food also represented that despite non-reaction on the first day due to the lack of digestive tracts, as the flatworm starts to regenerate, and the digestive system was able to perform its function again.

The process of regeneration has brought significant scientific improvement, especially in the field of medical science and regenerative studies. Throughout medical history, scientists and doctors had to deal with all kinds of cases that goes back to the primary purpose of fixing and healing the human body. The wounds ranging from larger impairments such as amputated limbs and broken bones down to small paper cuts and bruising all required the body to produce powers to heal itself. Using the current scientific technologies developed by humans was not sufficient to completely heal the wounds without the help of the human body. Therefore, investigating how the body actually uses mechanisms to heal itself is of vital importance. This is where regeneration comes into play. It is the completely natural way, inferring that it could possibly be developed and discovered within the human body, that enables the restoring of damaged or missing body parts. In 1951, a type of regenerative cell was discovered in a donor named Henrietta Lacks. Her cells were discovered to have the ability to continue reproducing even after the donor had passed away. This raised an uproar in the scientific field and ultimately led to tremendous eruptions of scientific improvements and innovation. Likewise, when the function of regeneration was discovered in the flatworms, scientists could develop further investigation on the topic of regeneration that may lead to further medical developments.

Specifically in this study, the flatworms were discovered to possess the ability to regenerate even without vital organs. This implied that what actually motivated and promoted their regrowth was the stem cells, or pluripotent stem cells that could possibly resemble any other functional cells of the body. This discovery could eventually lead scientists to investigate how humans would also develop similar mechanisms that enables the body to heal itself in times of amputation of limbs or serious injuries. However, the study also presented a problem to thus extended research, because the regrown parts of the flatworm that came out of the

body part without the vital organ do not seem to respond to food sources, meaning that they possibly lacked the necessary life functions. Though this may be due to the fact that their mouth hasn't developed yet, it could potentially pose a threat to the future research on regeneration. Overall, however, this study could lead to further investigation and research on regenerative stem cells and how the flatworm's display of regrowth could be reflected on humans and lead to better medical technologies.

References:

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